

ROLE OF MANGROVES IN COASTAL ECOSYSTEMS AND TRADITIONAL MEDICINE

Dr. Tippana Vijaya^{1*}, Dr. K. Madhusudana Rao²

PG Scholar^{1*}, Professor & HOD²,

Department of Dravya Guna, Dr. NRS Government Ayurvedic College, Vijayawada,
Andhra Pradesh, India.

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*Corresponding Author

Dr. Tippana Vijaya

PG Scholar, Department of Dravya
Guna, Dr. NRS Government
Ayurvedic College, Vijayawada,
Andhra Pradesh, India.

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ABSTRACT

Mangrove ecosystems are highly productive coastal habitats that maintain ecological balance and protect shorelines from erosion, cyclones, and tidal surges while supporting biodiversity and carbon sequestration. Species such as *Avicennia marina*, *Acanthus ilicifolius*, and *Bruguiera gymnorrhiza* possess significant medicinal potential due to the presence of bioactive phytochemicals, including flavonoids, tannins, saponins, and alkaloids. These phytochemicals exhibit anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antimicrobial, antidiabetic, analgesic, and wound-healing activities. Among them, *Avicennia marina* is widely distributed along the Indian coast and is traditionally used in ethnomedicine to manage skin diseases, wounds, inflammatory conditions, digestive disorders, and gum ailments. Commonly referred to as *Sāgarodbhūta* due to its marine habitat, it has traditional applications that are

increasingly supported by modern pharmacological studies, highlighting its therapeutic relevance and bridging traditional knowledge with contemporary scientific evidence.

AIM AND OBJECTIVE

- To identify and document the most commonly distributed mangrove species and their morphological features.

- To examine the phytochemical constituents and pharmacological activities of selected mangrove species, focusing on their anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and antioxidant properties.
- To explore the ethnobotanical significance and pharmacological potential of *Avicennia marina*, commonly referred to descriptively as *Sāgarodbhūta* due to its coastal habitat, and to bridge traditional folklore knowledge with modern scientific validation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

- Research articles and other scientific databases were reviewed to collect information on mangrove ecosystems, their ecological importance, common species, and their pharmacological activities.
- Literature on *Avicennia marina* (*Sāgarodbhūta*) was surveyed to document ethnobotanical uses and correlate traditional applications with modern pharmacological findings.

INTRODUCTION

Mangrove forests are unique coastal ecosystems found in tropical and subtropical regions, thriving in intertidal zones where land meets the sea. These forests are salt-tolerant coastal ecosystems found in tropical and subtropical intertidal regions. Adaptations such as pneumatophores, prop roots, and salt-excreting leaves enable them to survive in saline and waterlogged conditions.

Ecologically, mangroves play a vital role in maintaining environmental stability. Mangroves protect coastlines from erosion, cyclones, and tidal surges, while also serving as breeding habitats for diverse aquatic and terrestrial species. They additionally function as important carbon sinks and support biodiversity conservation.

In India, mangroves are widely distributed along the eastern and western coasts and the Andaman & Nicobar Islands, with major regions including the Sundarbans of West Bengal, Bhitarkanika in Odisha, Godavari and Krishna deltas of Andhra Pradesh, Pichavaram in Tamil Nadu, and the Gulf of Kachchh in Gujarat.

Commonly distributed mangrove species in India include:

1. *Avicennia marina* (Grey Mangrove)
2. *Bruguera gymnorrhiza* (Black Mangrove)

3. *Acanthus ilicifolius* (Sea Holy Mangrove)

These species not only contribute to shoreline protection and ecological balance but also possess ethnomedicinal and pharmacological significance, making mangrove forests ecologically and therapeutically valuable ecosystems.

Morphological Description of Mangrove Flora

1. *Avicennia marina* (Grey Mangrove)^[2]

Avicennia marina (grey mangrove) from the family Acanthaceae is a small to medium-sized evergreen tree/shrub (3–14 m) with smooth, light-grey/yellow-green bark, often found in intertidal zones. It is characterized by prominent pencil-like pneumatophores (10–38 cm), opposite, leathery leaves (silvery-white underneath, shiny green above), and small, yellow, fragrant flowers

- **Habit & Roots:** Usually 3–10 m tall, sometimes reaching 14 m, with a branched, rounded crown. It features an extensive horizontal root system with numerous, erect, pencil-like pneumatophores (breathing roots).
- **Bark:** Smooth, light grey or white, and thin with brittle, flaky patches.
- **Leaves:** Simple, opposite, and decussate (arranged in pairs at right angles). They are ovate to lanceolate, 1.8–10.2 cm long, coriaceous (leathery), glossy dark green on top, and covered in fine, silvery-white hairs underneath.
- **Flowers:** Small (5 mm), yellow to orange, and arranged in dense, terminal or axillary spikes. They are fragrant and have 4 petals and a 5-lobed calyx.
- **Fruit & Seeds:** The fruit is a flattened, ovoid, grey-green capsule (1.2–3 cm long) covered in fine, silvery hairs. It contains a single, large seed that often germinates while still attached to the tree (vivipary)

2. *Bruguiera gymnorrhiza* (Black Mangrove)

Bruguiera gymnorrhiza, commonly known as the Black Mangrove or Large-leafed Mangrove (family Rhizophoraceae), is a robust, evergreen tree known for its smooth to rough, dark, and often blackened bark. It typically grows 7–20 meters high, though it can reach up to 35 meters in optimal conditions.^[3]

- **Root System: Knee Roots:** The most distinctive feature, where lateral roots bend upward and then curve back down into the mud (pneumatophores), forming knee-like structures above the sediment to facilitate gas exchange.
Buttress Roots: The base of the trunk is buttressed, providing anchorage in waterlogged, anaerobic, and soft muddy soils.
- **Stem and Bark:** Trunk is Straight, with a diameter of 40–90 cm, and Bark is thick, smooth to fissured, and ranges in color from pale-brown to grey or dark, which gives the tree its common name.
- **Leaves:** Arrangement of leaves are opposite and crowded at the ends of the branches. Shape is Simple, thick, leathery (coriaceous), and elliptic-oblong, measuring 5–15 cm in length and 2–6 cm in width. Color is Glossy, dark green on the upper surface, and lighter green underneath.
- **Flowers:** Solitary (not in clusters), large, up to 4 cm long, and pendulous. Calyx is Distinctive, leathery, and dark red to pinkish-green, with 8–18 pointed, persistent lobes. Petals are Creamy white to pale yellow, turning brown with age, and, unlike other *Bruguiera* species, they have 3-4 distinct bristles at their tip.
- **Fruit:** A woody, turbinate (spinning-top shaped) berry, often 2 cm long. The seeds germinate while still attached to the parent tree. The hypocotyl (seedling) is elongated, cigar-shaped, ribbed, and can be up to 11–25 cm long, which drops and becomes embedded in the mud in an upright position.

3. *Acanthus ilicifolius* (Sea Holy Mangrove)

Acanthus ilicifolius, commonly known as Sea Holly, is a spiny, semi-woody perennial shrub belonging to the Acanthaceae family. It is a true mangrove species found in coastal, saline, or brackish water regions of tropical and subtropical areas. The plant is known for its glossy leaves with spiny margins, terminal spikes of blue/violet flowers, and capsules that explode to release seeds.^[4]

- **Habit:** A sprawling or erect shrub, usually 0.5–2 meters tall, but can reach 3 meters.
- **Stem:** Smooth, glossy green or slightly purple, with pairs of sharp spines at the nodes (leaf angles).
- **Leaves:** Simple, opposite, and leathery, resembling holly leaves, ranging from 9–30 cm in length. They are broadly lanceolate with spines on the margins and a prominent spine at the apex.
- **Flowers:** Arranged in dense, terminal spikes (10–20 cm long). Flowers are pale mauve, violet, or rarely white, featuring a 3-lobed lower lip and an almost absent upper lip.
- **Fruits:** Small (2–3 cm), smooth, oblong, or kidney-shaped capsules that are green to brown. They explosively dehisce to release 4 seeds.
- **Roots:** Possesses a fibrous root system to anchor in soft mud and sometimes develops aerial (prop) roots.

Bioactive Constituents and Pharmacological Activities of Mangrove Species

Mangroves are rich sources of diverse phytochemicals with significant pharmacological importance. Reported constituents include carbohydrates, amino acids, proteins, fatty acids, lipids, phenolic compounds, steroids, glycosides, triterpenes, alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins,

saponins, gums, and glues. Primary metabolites such as carbohydrates, amino acids, and proteins are essential for normal physiological functions, whereas secondary metabolites, including alkaloids, phenolics, steroids, and terpenoids, possess important toxicological, ecological, and therapeutic properties.

1. *Avicennia marina* (Grey Mangrove)^[6]

Avicennia marina is rich in bioactive phytoconstituents, including alkaloids, flavonoids, phenolics, tannins, glycosides, steroids, triterpenes, fatty acids, amino acids, and iridoid glycosides such as geniposide and mussaenoside, and related derivatives have been isolated from the leaves, along with compounds like 2'-cinnamoyl-mussaenoside, 10-O-(5-phenyl-2,4-pentadienoyl)-geniposide, and 7-O-(5-phenyl-2,4-pentadienoyl)-8-epiloganic acid. Triterpenoids like lupeol, taraxerol, and betulinic acid have also been isolated from the bark, indicating significant anti-cancerous and anti-inflammatory effects.

These phytochemicals contribute to the plant's diverse pharmacological activities, including antioxidant, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antidiabetic, anticancer, hepatoprotective, analgesic, and wound-healing effects. Traditionally, the plant has been used in the management of ulcers, abscesses, burns, rheumatism, smallpox, and snakebites, supporting its ethnomedicinal importance and potential for future drug development.

2. *Bruguiera gymnorrhiza* (Black Mangrove)

Bruguiera gymnorrhiza contains diverse phytoconstituents such as tannins, flavonoids, alkaloids, saponins, triterpenoids, steroids, phenolics, diterpenes, and iridoid glycosides. The bark is especially rich in tannins, contributing to its astringent, antioxidant, and antimicrobial properties.^[7]

Hepatic damage is involved in most cases of oxidative stress and is characterized by a progressive evolution from steatosis to chronic hepatitis, fibrosis, cirrhosis, and hepatocellular carcinoma.^[8] The plant-derived antioxidants, particularly polyphenols, could be correlated with oxidative stress defense and hepatoprotection.^[9] Furthermore, mangrove is a rich source of novel compounds with powerful antioxidant properties. The Leaves of *B. gymnorrhiza* is a rich source of gallic acid, quercetin, and coumarin, and there is considerable data to support their antioxidant and hepatoprotective actions. *In vitro* antioxidant studies show *B. gymnorrhiza* has strong reducing abilities and DPPH radical scavenging properties, and also has the capacity to inhibit generations of ABTS⁺ radicals and hydroxyl radicals. It is

believed that hydroxyl radicals hamper normal liver functions by damaging and breaking DNA strands in hepatic tissues. Moreover, *B. gymnorrhiza* has nitric oxide and superoxide radical scavenging abilities, and thereby it has strong antioxidant properties. Earlier, it was reported that the stems and the roots of this mangrove have a potent antioxidant role on polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon-treated tissues.^[10]

3. *Acanthus ilicifolius* (Sea Holy Mangrove)

Acanthus ilicifolius contains diverse bioactive phytoconstituents including alkaloids, triterpenoid saponins, benzoxazinoids, pentacyclic triterpenoids, sterols, and glycosides. Phytochemical studies have identified compounds such as acanthicifoline, 2-benzoxazolinone, bisoxazolinone, and ilicifolioside C from different plant parts and solvent extracts, contributing to its rich medicinal and pharmacological potential.^[11]

The pharmacological activities of *Acanthus ilicifolius* are closely related to these compounds. Flavone glycosides, lignans, and phenolic derivatives contribute to strong antioxidant activity by neutralizing free radicals. Triterpenoid saponins and pentacyclic triterpenoids are responsible for their anti-inflammatory and anti-arthritic effects through inhibition of inflammatory mediators.^[12]

Acanthicifoline and related alkaloids support analgesic and anti-inflammatory actions, while benzoxazolinone and benzoxazinoid derivatives exhibit notable antimicrobial and protective activities. Sterols and glycosides further enhance its hepatoprotective and wound-healing properties. Thus, the synergistic interaction of these phytoconstituents forms the biochemical basis for the therapeutic importance of *Acanthus ilicifolius* in inflammatory, infectious, and oxidative stress-related conditions.^[13]

Protective Role of Mangrove Forests in Ecosystem Stability^[14]

Mangrove ecosystems function as natural coastal defense systems by reducing wave energy, storm surges, and water flow through their dense root networks and vegetation structure. Morphological features such as prop roots, pneumatophores, and dense canopies enhance sediment stabilization, decrease erosion, and limit inland flooding.

Mangroves also trap suspended sediments, promote land formation, and improve soil stability, thereby helping counter shoreline retreat and sea-level rise. In addition, they

regulate hydrology by storing and gradually releasing excess water during storms, reducing saline intrusion and flood damage.

Collectively, the structural complexity, sediment-binding capacity, and hydrodynamic resistance provided by mangrove forests make them indispensable components of coastal ecosystem stability. Their ability to attenuate waves, stabilize shorelines, regulate flooding, and support biodiversity demonstrates their integral role in maintaining environmental equilibrium and enhancing the adaptive capacity of ecosystems in the face of climatic and anthropogenic pressures. Overall, mangroves play a crucial role in the maintenance of coastal ecological balance.

Ethnobotanical Significance and Modern Validation of *Avicennia marina* (Sāgarodbhūta)

Avicennia marina, sometimes descriptively associated with the term *Sāgarodbhūta* due to its coastal habitat, easily available mangrove species used in coastal ethnomedicine. Although not directly mentioned in classical Ayurvedic Nighaṅṭus under this name, it has been traditionally utilized by coastal healers based on local knowledge.

Different plant parts are employed for common ailments, particularly skin infections, wounds, and inflammatory conditions. The bark is valued for its astringent and wound-cleansing properties, while fresh leaves are mainly used for external applications. Traditional preparations are often combined with ingredients such as ginger, black pepper, honey, sesame oil, or coconut oil to improve therapeutic effectiveness.

Common traditional practices (elaborated)

- **Bark Decoction (Kwath):** Dried bark (10–20 g) boiled in water and reduced to half was used as a wash for ulcers, chronic wounds, and skin eruptions. Internally, small quantities were administered for digestive sluggishness and dampness-related disorders.
- **Leaf Paste Application:** Fresh leaves were crushed into a paste and applied over shell cuts, fish-spine injuries, boils, and localized swelling to reduce inflammation and promote healing.
- **Powder (Churna):** Finely powdered bark or leaves (approximately 3–6 g per day for adults) mixed with warm water or honey was consumed for mild digestive support and to counter sluggish metabolism in humid climates.

- **Infused Oil Preparations:** Bark powder gently heated in sesame or coconut oil (1:5 ratio) was filtered and applied externally over minor ulcers, joint discomfort, or cracked skin.
- **Simple Leaf Infusion (Herbal Tea):** Dried leaves (2–3 g) steeped in hot water were consumed as a mild antioxidant and digestive beverage, especially during seasonal transitions.^[15]

Though largely preserved in regional practice and secondary ethnobotanical sources, these applications demonstrate the plant's practical therapeutic value and its enduring relevance in coastal traditional healthcare systems.

Modern scientific understanding provides supportive validation for these traditional uses. Extracts of *Avicennia marina* demonstrate significant anti-inflammatory and analgesic activity, including reduction of swelling comparable to standard anti-inflammatory agents and inhibition of key inflammatory mediators such as prostaglandins and nitric oxide. The plant exhibits strong wound-healing properties, promoting faster wound contraction, enhanced collagen deposition, and reduced inflammatory cell infiltration, aligning with its traditional application in cuts and ulcers. Its rich content of phenolics and flavonoids contributes to marked antioxidant activity, showing high free radical scavenging potential and protection against oxidative damage. Additionally, the presence of bioactive compounds supports antimicrobial action, including inhibition of common pathogenic bacteria and biofilm formation, which explains its effectiveness in treating skin infections and minor wounds in humid coastal environments. Together, these modern findings substantiate the empirical wisdom of coastal communities and bridge traditional ethnobotanical knowledge with contemporary pharmacological evidence.

CONCLUSION

The present study highlights three important mangrove species—*Avicennia marina*, *Bruguiera gymnorrhiza*, and *Acanthus ilicifolius*—focusing on their adaptive morphology, phytochemical constituents, and pharmacological activities. These species possess specialized features such as pneumatophores, prop roots, salt-secreting leaves, and vivipary, enabling survival in saline coastal environments. Phytochemical studies have identified flavonoids, phenolics, tannins, alkaloids, triterpenoids, and glycosides responsible for anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, antioxidant, analgesic, wound-healing, and gastroprotective properties.

Among them, *Avicennia marina* (*Sāgarodbhūta*) is widely used in coastal folklore medicine through bark, leaf, and topical preparations. Scientific validation of its therapeutic properties supports its ethnomedicinal importance. Thus, mangroves are significant not only for coastal protection and ecological balance but also as promising sources of medicinal compounds, underscoring the need for continued interdisciplinary research and conservation efforts.

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